

Synthesis of 2-[4-(3,5-Dimethyl-1(H)-Pyrazole)phenyl]-4H-1-Benzo(B)pyran-4-One and its Derivatives

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Synthesis of heteroanalogues substituted at the position 2 of 4H-1-benzopyran-4-one viz., 2-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)phenyl], 7-hydroxy-2-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)phenyl] and 5,7-dihydroxy-2-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)phenyl]-4H-1-benzo(b)pyran-4-ones have been described.

THOUGH most of the derivatives of benzopyran-4-ones are natural products, a few synthetic ones are also found to be biologically active¹. 4H-1-benzopyran-4-one having heterocyclic substituents at either 2 or 3 positions are reported to have coronary dilatory activity²⁻⁴, muscular relaxation effect⁵, anticarcinogenic activity⁶, spasmolytic activity^{7,8} and antimicrobial activity⁹⁻¹². Hence, it was thought of interest to synthesise a few heterocyclic analogues of 2-phenyl-benzopyran-4-ones in order to screen their antimicrobial and pharmacological activity.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of 2-heterosubstituted-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (III a, b, c). Three different methods were employed for synthesis of esters (I a, b, c).

- 2-Hydroxy acetophenone was reacted with acid chloride of 3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-(4-carboxy phenyl) pyrazole¹³ in dry pyridine at about 50°.
- 2-Hydroxy acetophenone was refluxed with acid chloride of 3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-(4-carboxy phenyl)pyrazole in dry acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.
- The acid was directly reacted with 2-hydroxy acetophenone in dry pyridine using POCl₃ as the condensing agent to obtain the corresponding O-acyl ester (I). Similar methods used with 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone and 2,4,6-trihydroxy acetophenone.

The yields of O-acyl ester (I, a-c) obtained by the method A varied from 12-20% while the method B gave either no desired product or in negligible quantity. The method C however, gave excellent yields of the ester, varying from 90-96%.

The above esters were then subjected to Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement to give 1,3-diketones (II a-c), which on cyclisation in glacial acetic acid containing 1-2% (v/v) conc. hydrochloric acid afforded the desired compounds (III a-c) in excellent yields varying from 87-98%.

Experimental

All m.p.s were determined in open capillaries in a paraffin bath and are uncorrected. The structures (III a-c) are supported by elemental analysis and spectral data. UV spectra (λ max in nm) recorded in methanol, ir spectra (ν max in cm⁻¹) in KBr pellets/Nujol and nmr (chemical shifts in δ ppm) in CDCl₃.

Preparation of O-acyl ester (I a-c) :

Method A :

General procedure :

To a solution of the appropriate hydroxy acetophenone (0.005 mole) in dry pyridine was added acid chloride (0.005 mole) and the mixture stirred until a clear solution was obtained. After stirring for 1 hr at 50°, the solution was left overnight. The contents were then poured into cold hydrochloric acid (2 N). On stirring for some time the mass solidified and was filtered and washed with water. The product was triturated with cold

caustic soda solution (1%), filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from a suitable solvent.

- (a) 2-[4-(3,5-Dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)benzoyloxy]acetophenone. Colourless needles from ethanol, m.p. 85°, yield 13%. (Found: C, 71.61; H, 5.73; N, 8.33. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2O_5$ requires C, 71.68; H, 5.39; N, 3.38%).
- (b) 2,4-Di-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)benzoyloxy]acetophenone. Colourless needles from methanol, m.p. 134-5°, yield 18%. (Found: C, 69.81; H, 5.30; N, 10.14. $C_{38}H_{36}N_4O_8$ requires C, 70.07; H, 5.11; N, 10.22%).
- (c) 2,4,6-Tri-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)benzoyloxy]acetophenone. Yellowish needles from ethanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 81-2°, yield 20%. (Found: C, 69.42; H, 4.82; N, 11.14. $C_{44}H_{40}N_6O_7$ requires C, 69.29; H, 4.99; N, 11.02%).

Method B :

Appropriate acetophenone (0.005 mole) and the acid chloride were dissolved in dry acetone (50 ml). Freshly ignited K_2CO_3 (3 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 hr on a water bath, after which the solution was filtered and the residue washed with dry acetone. Acetone was removed under reduced pressure and the product, purified as in method (A) yielded a small amount of ester (I a-c).

Method C :

A solution of appropriate acetophenone (0.065 mole) and the acid (0.07 mole) in dry pyridine (50 ml) was cooled to about 10-15° and $POCl_3$ (4 ml) added to it dropwise with constant stirring while maintaining the temperature between 10-15°. After stirring at R.T. for 2 hr, the reaction mixture was treated with cold HCl solution (2 N) and the product separated was filtered, washed successively with water, cold NaOH (2%) and water and crystallized from suitable solvent to give I a-c, with yields 96%, 91%, 90%, respectively. The identity of the compounds was checked by tlc and m.m.p. with the samples obtained in method A.

1,3-Diketones (II a-c) :

General procedure :

A mixture of I (0.01 mole) and powdered KOH (0.03 mole) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature when it turned into a yellowish to brown viscous paste in a short while. It was further stirred for about 30 min and acidified with cold dilute acetic acid (2 N). The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from methanol to give II a-c.

IIa—Pale yellow needles, m.p. 137-8°, yield 80%. IIb—Brownish needles, m.p. 145-7°, yield 82%. IIc—Brown needles, m.p. 154°, yield 70%.

All compounds II a-c were freely soluble in alkali and gave positive ferric reaction.

Preparation of 2-heterosubstituted-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (III a-c) :

General procedure :

1,3-Diketo compound (II a-c) (0.001 mole) was dissolved in 20 ml glacial acetic acid containing 1-2% (v/v) of conc. hydrochloric acid. The solution was refluxed for 1 hr, cooled and poured into crushed ice with stirring. The separated solid was filtered, washed with dilute $NaHCO_3$ (2 N) followed by water. The products were then repeatedly crystallized from suitable solvents until single spot on tlc.

III a : 2-[4-(3,5-Dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one. Colourless needles from ethanol, violet fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 146°, yield 95%. (Found: C, 76.14; H, 5.22; N, 8.71. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2O_3$ requires C, 75.95; H, 5.06; N, 8.86%). UV : 275, 312; ir : 1630 (C=O); 1120, 1220 (C-O-C); 1550, 1600 (γ -pyrone ring); 2910, 3030 (=C pyrazole); nmr : 2.24

CH₃

(s, 3H, 3-CH₃ of pyrazole), 2.4 (s, 3H, 5-CH₃ of pyrazole), 6.0 (s, 1H, H-3), 6.8 (s, 1H, H-4 of pyrazole), 7.0-8.0 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

III b : 7-Hydroxy-2-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one. Pale yellow needles from methanol, violet fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 158°, yield 85%. (Found: C, 72.15; H, 4.89; N, 8.48. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2O_4$ requires C, 72.29; H, 4.82; N, 8.43%). UV : 278, 312; ir : 3400 (-OH); 1680 (C=O); 1110, 1270 (C-O-C); 1550-1605 (γ -pyrone ring); 2920, 3030 (=C pyrazole).

CH₃

III c : 5,7-Dihydroxy-2-[4-(3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-pyrazole)phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one. Pale yellow needles from dioxane, blue fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 300°, yield 83%. (Found: C, 69.14; H, 4.55; N, 8.11. $C_{20}H_{18}N_2O_4$ requires C, 68.98; H, 4.60; N, 8.05%). UV : 270, 320; ir : 3200-3350 (-OH); 1655 (C=O); 1110, 1245 (C-O-C); 1550, 1600 (γ -pyrone ring); 2920, 3035 (=C pyrazole).

CH₃

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FERNANDES, DESAI & NADKARNY : SYNTHESIS OF 2-[4-(3,5-DIMETHYL-1(H)-PYRAZOLE)PHENYL]- ETC.

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